

Bengaluru
Roadmap and Action Plan on
**Diamond Open
Access**

Global Summit
Diamond Open Access
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Colophon

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'Bengaluru Roadmap and Action Plan on Diamond Open Access'

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Preamble

The [3rd Global Summit on Diamond Open Access](#)¹ was convened in Bengaluru from 2 to 6 February 2026. Discussions during the Summit reaffirmed the view that scholarly knowledge is a public good and that scholarly communication should remain governed by the scholarly communities that create and sustain it.

Diamond Open Access is a community governed² model that enables equitable participation in global knowledge production, operating on a no-fee basis for both authors and readers. A coordinated global transition toward this model is supported through public investment, shared infrastructure, and responsible governance.

All stakeholders - governments and policy makers, research funding and performing organisations, scholarly communities, community-led infrastructure providers, universities, evaluation bodies, libraries, and regional training hubs - are invited to engage with the Bengaluru Roadmap and to contribute to strengthening the global knowledge commons.

The 'Conclusions and Way Forward' of the 1st Global Summit on Diamond Open Access (Toluca, México, 18–23 October 2023), the Manifesto on Science as a Global Public Good (2023), and the 'Toluca-Cape Town Declaration' resulting from the 2nd Global Summit on Diamond Open Access (8–14 December 2024) contributed to ongoing international discussions on scholarly communication as a public good, community-led approaches to Diamond Open Access, and more equitable and inclusive models of knowledge dissemination. These processes and outcomes serve as an important reference point for the 3rd Global Summit on Diamond Open Access and the development of the Bengaluru Roadmap.

Diamond Open Access reflects the principles affirmed in Articles 19 and 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, including the rights to see, receive and impart information to participate in and the benefit from scientific progress and its applications. It aligns with the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021), the UN Global Digital Compact (2024),

and the Council of the European Union Conclusions (2023), which recognise knowledge as a global public good and call for equitable and inclusive access to scientific outputs.

The 3rd Global Summit brought together 347 participants from 36 countries over five days of plenary deliberations, thematic workshops, and working group sessions, with 168 attending in person and 179 participating online, including invited speakers and contributors who participated through virtual and recorded interventions. Discussions addressed the governance and sustainability of Diamond Open Access infrastructure; research assessment reform; equity, multilingualism, and bibliodiversity; early career researchers; metadata standards, persistent identifiers, and interoperability; repositories and preprints; and capacity-building across disciplines and regions.

The Bengaluru Roadmap offers a shared direction for action on several fronts without prescribing a single model. It recognises the diversity of scholarly cultures, institutional arrangements, and policy environments, and provides a common framework that stakeholders can adapt to regional, national, disciplinary, and institutional contexts while remaining aligned with a coherent global vision.

The Roadmap addresses multiple stakeholder groups. Governments and policy makers are encouraged to embed Diamond Open Access within national science policies and direct public investment toward community governed knowledge systems, in order to preserve the sovereignty of the scholarly community over the full scholarly communication ecosystem, including editorial processes, publishing infrastructures, metadata, and dissemination systems. Research funding organisations are encouraged to shift from short-term project grants to sustained structural investment. Research performing organisations, scholarly communities, and community-led infrastructure providers are supported with a framework to strengthen policies, capacity, coordination, and shared services, in a manner consistent with governance in the public interest.

1. For the purpose of this document, Diamond Open Access is a scholar-led and community-owned scholarly publishing model without costs for authors or readers, making knowledge available as a global public good via non-commercial infrastructures. It promotes equity, inclusion, sustainability, multilingualism, and bibliodiversity, aligning with the Budapest Open Access Initiative-BOAI20, the UNESCO 2021 Recommendation on Open Science, the Action Plan for Diamond Open Access, and the UN Global Digital Compact. Diamond OA is supported by governments, universities, public institutions, and funding organisations whose mission includes performing or promoting research and scholarship for the benefit of society.
2. In the context of this Roadmap, the term 'community' refers to the scholarly and research communities – including researchers, editors, reviewers, librarians, institutional repository managers, scholarly societies, and non-commercial infrastructure providers – who collectively produce, evaluate, and disseminate knowledge as a public good. In the Roadmap, notions such as 'community governed', 'community-led', and 'community-owned' should be understood as a function of this definition.

Reimagining Scholarly Publishing for Equity and Inclusion: Towards a Global Knowledge Commons

Diamond Open Access works to restore scholarly communication to its public purpose, ensuring that knowledge remains a public good, openly accessible and governed by the scholarly communities that hold sovereign authority over the communication process. Researchers and institutions across regions and disciplines increasingly recognise that publishing models structured around commercial incentives are no longer sufficient to serve the long-term interests of research communities or society.

As such, its implementation is both a policy challenge and a shared global responsibility. It requires a shift from short-term service and content procurement towards sustained public investment in shared infrastructure, owned and governed by scholarly communities in the public

interest. A global knowledge commons requires that responsibility for sustaining it be shared equitably among all stakeholders. Diamond Open Access offers the framework for this transformation, and the Bengaluru Summit calls on the global scholarly community and its partners to build it.

Beyond the absence of fees for authors and readers, Diamond Open Access is community governed, commons-based, and care-centred, led by scholarly communities, with decisions made with special attention to those who have been historically and epistemically excluded. This care-centred approach prioritises relationships, reciprocity, and scholarly work relevant to local contexts, rather than publication speed, volume, or externally imposed standards.

Global Commitment, Governance, and Shared Responsibility

Securing the long-term sustainability of Diamond Open Access is a shared responsibility across governments, research funding organisations, institutions, and scholarly communities. Governments play a central role: public investment allows Diamond Open Access to remain owned by and accountable to the scientific community and society, upholding the principle that scientific knowledge is a shared global good. Governments are invited to direct resources within their national systems to redirect a defined and predictable share of existing publishing expenditure toward community governed, non-commercial infrastructures, and to engage actively in inter-governmental coordination efforts that connect national systems within a coherent, inclusive, and community governed global knowledge ecosystem.

Governments are encouraged to embed these commitments in national policy frameworks, legal instruments, and funding strategies, including the long-term preservation of knowledge. Grounding access to scientific knowledge in human rights frameworks strengthens the legitimacy of reform and reaffirms the responsibility of states to keep scientific knowledge openly accessible and under the governance of the scholarly community, with decision-making authority resting with research

communities and publicly funded infrastructures protected from commercial acquisition and enclosure. Governments are called on to support the systemic conditions that allow Diamond Open Access to function and grow, including:

- ♦ Contributing to the reform of research evaluation systems to recognise Diamond Open Access outputs on equal terms with outputs in commercially indexed venues.
- ♦ Building a shared evidence base to inform policy and demonstrate the societal value of open knowledge.
- ♦ Ensuring that standards and interoperability frameworks serve all communities, including those with limited resources.
- ♦ Respecting the governance sovereignty of scholarly publishing within research communities.
- ♦ Promoting shared, community governed quality frameworks that strengthen research integrity without excluding under-resourced journals and institutions.

Building, Supporting and Sustaining Diamond Open Access Infrastructure

Diamond Open Access infrastructure is a core component of the scholarly communication system and a structural pillar of the global knowledge commons. Building and sustaining it requires deliberate public policy initiatives, structural funding, and coordinated governance aligned with scholarly values.

Diamond Open Access is sustained not only by platforms and repositories, but by people. Editorial teams, reviewers, technical staff, metadata specialists, repository managers, and community co-ordinators form the human infrastructure of this ecosystem, and their contributions deserve structured recognition and support.

Stakeholders are invited to invest in shared capacity through structured training programmes, editorial hubs, communities of practice, peer-learning networks, and formal recognition of editorial and peer-review labour within workload models and promotion frameworks.

Stable, structural funding from public and philanthropic sources, as well as innovative models such as 'freemium' arrangements, wherein a free service charges money for additional features, is important to sustain Diamond Open Access over the long term. Short-term competitive grants create precarity and fragmentation. Governments, research funding organisations, and institutions are encouraged to redirect a defined and predictable share of existing publishing expenditures away from Article Processing Charges and Transformative Agreements and towards sustaining community-owned platforms, repositories, preservation services, metadata systems, and shared editorial support. Open-source technologies and pooled infrastructure are recommended to reduce costs, increase transparency, and protect scholarly sovereignty.

Governance must be transparent and accountable, and community-owned structures play an important role in this respect. Clear public-interest mandates, collective oversight, and safeguards against commercial acquisition help prevent the concentration of power and the enclosure of publicly funded infrastructure. Legal community ownership, where feasible, is encouraged as a means of securing long-term autonomy.

The sustainability of Diamond Open Access depends on coordinated and interoperable ecosystems rather than isolated solutions. Existing open infrastructures can be strengthened and aligned rather than duplicated, with greater emphasis on global collaboration and multilateral investment. Shared standards, interoperable metadata frameworks, multilingual accessibility, and international communities of practice contribute to building resilience at scale, while bibliodiversity and regional autonomy are preserved within this Roadmap for global coordination.

Quality, trust, and research integrity must be embedded within platform governance. Community governed frameworks for editorial standards, peer review transparency, and responsible AI use can develop progressively and equitably, ensuring that standards raise quality without excluding under-resourced journals.

Diamond Open Access journals and repositories are societal assets that connect science with society, enable locally-grounded knowledge production, preserve linguistic and cultural diversity, and support evidence-based policy making. All stakeholders are invited to communicate their public value beyond academia to secure sustained political and institutional commitment.

Research Assessment and Diamond Open Access

The success of Diamond Open Access depends on research evaluation systems evolving in parallel. Current metric-driven regimes, heavily reliant on journal-based indicators and commercially indexed venues, create structural disincentives for publishing in Diamond Open Access publications, platforms, and repositories. Reforming research

assessment is therefore central to its legitimacy and sustainability.

Assessment bodies and institutions are invited to move beyond exclusive reliance on journal impact factors and quantitative output metrics, adopting qualitative, context-sensitive, and nar-

rative-based approaches that recognise the full research package: datasets, software, models, protocols, exhibitions, knowledge transfer, policy translation, and demonstrable social impact. Editors, peer reviewers, and infrastructure stewards need to be recognised as equal contributors to the scholarly discussion.

Governments and institutions are encouraged to review and, where appropriate, remove regulatory and normative barriers that privilege commercial metrics. They can ensure that Open Science road-

maps and national research strategies recognise Diamond Open Access publications, multilingual scholarship, and community governed venues as credible outputs.

All stakeholders are invited to build a stronger evidence base that demonstrates the inefficiencies, inequities, and societal costs of current publishing and evaluation systems, and to support policy reform grounded in academic freedom, social justice, and public accountability.

Early Career Researchers and Diamond Open Access

Early Career Researchers (ECRs) are central to the future of Diamond Open Access. While they are disproportionately affected by current incentive systems, they represent the generation that will determine whether community governed publishing becomes the norm.

Metric-driven evaluation systems expose ECRs to genuine professional risk when publishing in Diamond Open Access channels. Governments, institutions, and research funding organisations are therefore invited to protect ECRs from structural disadvantage while enabling them to lead this transformation. Universities and research performing organisations are called on to inte-

grate knowledge of ethical publishing, open peer review, data stewardship, and community governance into doctoral and post-doctoral training programmes; formally recognise editorial and peer-review contributions in hiring and promotion decisions; and to provide sustained support for ECR-led initiatives and meaningful ECR representation in governance bodies.

All stakeholders are encouraged to ensure that Diamond Open Access does not rely on precarious or invisible labour, and that redirecting public funding toward community-owned infrastructures reflects a shared commitment to the next generation of scholars.

Responsible Use of Artificial Intelligence

The development and deployment of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in scholarly communication requires progressive and equitable integration, with strong safeguards to protect the integrity and openness of the scholarly record.

It is expected that AI-assisted tools for translation, editorial support, metadata generation, and discovery systems will facilitate accessibility and efficiency when used responsibly and under rigorous and ethical human oversight. Responsible use is also essential to ensure proper recognition of authorship and intellectual contribution, as AI systems trained on openly available scholarly outputs are discouraged from obscuring or appropriating the work of researchers and research teams. Clearer norms for attribution, transparency in the use of AI training data, and

mechanisms to acknowledge and credit original authors will provide further safeguards. At the same time, there is growing concern that AI systems may absorb openly accessible scholarly content and repurpose it within closed, commercial platforms without appropriate attribution, transparency, or reciprocity. Such practices risk undermining the principles of openness and the collective investment that sustains public knowledge infrastructures.

The Roadmap therefore invites all stakeholders to develop responsible AI governance frameworks that ensure transparency in data use, protect open scholarly resources from enclosure within proprietary systems, and uphold the values of Diamond Open Access and the global knowledge commons.

Monitoring and Continuity

The Bengaluru Roadmap fulfils its purpose when its orientations are translated into measurable actions. This document serves as a framework for implementation across each Action Area. The Roadmap defines the strategic direction and provides a basis for sustained operational follow-up. In particular, the actors below are invited to consider the following:

- ◇ Governments and institutions are invited to publish periodic reports on Diamond Open Access progress, tracking policy adoption, funding flows, infrastructure development, and research assessment reform.
- ◇ Regional and national coordination mechanisms are encouraged to serve as anchoring points for monitoring journal development, adoption of quality standards, and training activities.
- ◇ Inter-governmental organisations are called on, within their respective mandates, to provide coordinated support to Member States for the development of policies and the strengthening of institutional capacities related to Open Science.
- ◇ All stakeholders are invited to ensure that the monitoring framework for the UNESCO 2021 Recommendation on Open Science adequately captures and reflects the role of Diamond Open Access.

Recommended Key Actions

Based on discussions at the Bengaluru Summit, six priority areas were identified in which coordinated action can strengthen Diamond Open Access at global, regional, national, and institutional levels.

Each Action Area engages multiple stakeholder groups; none rests with a single actor. Equity, the meaningful inclusion of Early Career Researchers, and the protection of community governed publishing from commercial control are integrated across all six areas as cross-cutting commitments.

The long-term viability of Diamond Open Access depends on structural reform, sustained public investment, and aligned incentives throughout the research ecosystem. These Action Areas translate the shared principles affirmed in this Roadmap into coordinated, stakeholder-specific³ orientations, designed for adaptation across national, regional, disciplinary, and institutional contexts, while remaining coherent with the global framework articulated at the Bengaluru Summit.

The Bengaluru Roadmap and Action Plan affirm that Diamond Open Access is a proven and growing structural transformation of scholarly communication, already practised across every region of the world by thousands of journals,

repositories, platforms, scholarly societies, and research communities. What is required is structural public investment; aligned policy environments; reformed research assessment systems; recognised and remunerated human capacity; and coordinated global governance that would allow Diamond Open Access to fulfil its potential as the leading model through which publicly-funded knowledge is produced, evaluated, disseminated, and preserved.

The Bengaluru Summit reaffirms the core conviction that has united the global Diamond Open Access community since the first global summit in Toluca: that scientific knowledge is a public good and a human right; that scholarly communication is governed by the communities that produce and depend on it; and that building the infrastructure for that vision is a shared responsibility of scholars, institutions, research funding organisations, governments, and society.

We invite all stakeholders to engage with this Roadmap and Action Plan, to translate its orientations into concrete initiatives within their own contexts, and to return to the next Global Summit on Diamond Open Access having made measurable progress toward the global knowledge commons we are building together.

Action Area 1: Foster policy recognition and public interest governance

Lead Stakeholders: Governments and policy makers; research funding organisations.

Contributing Stakeholders: Research performing organisations; scholarly communities; community-led infrastructure providers.

Diamond Open Access should be recognised as a core, community governed component of national and global scholarly communication systems.

Governments are encouraged to support its long-term sustainability through policy and legal frameworks aligned with the principle that publicly funded knowledge is a public good.

Public-interest governance plays a central role in ensuring that scholarly communication remains owned and steered by the research community, and accountable to society. Governments are further invited to engage in international coordination to support a coherent, inclusive, and community governed global knowledge infrastructure.

3. In this document, we will refer to nine types of stakeholders in Diamond Open Access: (1) governments and policymakers, (2) research funding organisations, (3) research performing organisations, (4) scholarly communities, (5) community-led infrastructure providers, (6) universities, (7) evaluation bodies, (8) libraries, and (9) regional training hubs.

◇ Recognition and integration into public policy and funding frameworks

Lead Stakeholders are encouraged to formally recognise Diamond Open Access as a core component of a public, community governed scholarly communication system, and to embed it within national open science policies, research strategies, infrastructure roadmaps, higher education legislation, and public funding frameworks.

◇ Legal anchoring and protection as a public good

Governments and policy makers are invited to anchor equitable access to scientific knowledge in normative and legal frameworks as a matter of human rights and public interest; and to establish safeguards that prevent the privatisation or enclosure of publicly-funded scholarly infrastructure.

◇ Coordinated development through adaptable roadmaps

Lead Stakeholders are encouraged to establish or strengthen national and regional coordination mechanisms with clear mandates, inclusive stakeholder participation, and sustainable resourcing; and to develop aligned roadmaps that contribute to a shared global vision for Diamond Open Access, while preserving flexibility to reflect local, disciplinary, and institutional contexts.

◇ Community-led governance with transparency and safeguards

Governments and research funding organisations are invited to enable research communities and institutions to govern and sustain Diamond Open Access through transparent, accountable, and participatory governance models; to protect scholarly publishing sovereignty by ensuring systems remain locally grounded yet globally connected; and to support oversight and review mechanisms that prevent enclosure, acquisition, or vendor lock-in.

◇ Monitoring, accountability, and continuous improvement

Lead Stakeholders are encouraged to establish periodic monitoring, evaluation, and public reporting mechanisms to track progress; ensure accountability; and inform iterative development of Diamond Open Access ecosystems at national, regional, and global levels.

Action Area 2: Provide sustainable and predictable funding

Lead Stakeholders: Research funding organisations; governments, research performing organisations.

Contributing Stakeholders: Research performing organisations; community-led infrastructure providers.

Diamond Open Access infrastructure should be treated as a structural public good benefiting from sustained and predictable public investment. Current expenditure on subscriptions, Article Processing Charges and Transformative Agreements represents a significant allocation of public resources to models that are economically inefficient and inequitable.

A transition to Diamond Open Access would benefit from the progressive re-direction of these resources toward community governed, non-com-

mercial infrastructures and services that support the full research lifecycle.

In parallel, policy frameworks should prioritise the long-term strengthening of existing Diamond Open Access systems, sustained through institutional in-kind contribution, particularly those anchored in public universities functioning as core infrastructure, emphasising recognition, protection, and reinforcement rather than transition.

◇ Coordinated reinvestment in community governed funding

Lead Stakeholders are encouraged to progressively redirect a defined and predictable share of existing subscription, Article Processing Charges and Transformative Agreements expenditure toward coordinated, community governed, non-commercial funding mechanisms at national and international levels. This shift can draw on the success of existing regional systems where APC mechanisms are minimal or absent, despite their rising prevalence over recent years, ensuring long-term sustainability while safeguarding editorial independence and community governance.

◇ Structural, inclusive, and long-term funding models

Lead Stakeholders are invited to establish multi-year, structural funding frameworks that support the full ecosystem of Diamond Open Access, including editorial teams, technical staff, infrastructure coordination, scholarly societies, and Early Career Researcher-led initiatives, thereby reducing reliance on short-term project funding and precarious or unpaid labour.

◇ Shared infrastructure and service mutualisation

Lead Stakeholders and community-led infrastructure providers are encouraged to invest in and sustain shared, community governed infrastructures and services, such as publishing platforms, repositories, long-term preservation networks, metadata systems, and editorial support, while mutualising essential operations (including copyediting, XML production, accessibility compliance, and archiving) to enhance efficiency, interoperability, and resilience across contexts.

◇ Evidence-based advocacy and value communication

All stakeholders are invited to communicate the cost-efficiency and societal value of Diamond Open Access through transparent, evidence-based advocacy, fostering broad alignment among governments, research funding organisations, institutions, and scholarly communities.

Action Area 3: Reform Research Assessment

Lead Stakeholders: Governments, research funding and performing organisations, universities; evaluation bodies.

Contributing Stakeholders: Policymakers; scholarly communities.

The transition to Diamond Open Access requires structural reform of research evaluation systems that currently privilege journal-based prestige metrics and commercially-indexed venues. These systems distort research priorities, disadvantage

equitable and community governed publishing models, and are misaligned with the public interest objectives of research. Reforming research assessment is therefore foundational to the legitimacy and sustainability of Diamond Open Access.

◇ Reform assessment frameworks to move beyond journal-based metrics

Lead stakeholders are encouraged to move beyond reliance on journal-based indicators (such as impact factors and inclusion in commercial indexing systems) and to decouple research assessment from journal prestige, adopting in their place qualitative, narrative-based, and context-sensitive approaches that recognise the full diversity of scholarly contributions. These reforms are encouraged to align with international initiatives (e.g. the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA); the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) The Latin American Forum on Research Assessment (FOLEC)), while ensuring accountability for implementation and adaptability to local contexts.

◇ Broaden the recognition of scholarly contributions within assessment systems

Lead stakeholders are invited to explicitly recognise a wide range of research outputs and practices, including Diamond Open Access publications; multilingual scholarship; editorial and peer review work; infrastructure stewardship; datasets; software; and societal impact, as legitimate contributions. This expanded recognition could be embedded in national and institutional research assessment policies, aligned with Open Science and Diamond Open Access principles.

◇ Enable inclusive and equitable participation in assessment reform

Lead stakeholders are called on to provide targeted training and guidance for researchers, evaluators, and assessment bodies on responsible research evaluation and Open Science practices. They are also encouraged to adapt evaluation criteria and expectations to protect Early Career Researchers and other potentially disadvantaged groups during the transition, ensuring fair and inclusive implementation.

◇ Strengthen the evidence base for assessment reform

All stakeholders are invited to support research and evidence-building on the systemic effects of metric-driven evaluation systems, and on the effectiveness of alternative assessment models, to inform continuous improvement and policy adaptation.

◇ Ensure transparency and accountability in reform implementation

Lead stakeholders are encouraged to monitor, evaluate, and publicly report on progress in reforming research assessment frameworks, in alignment with Open Science and Diamond Open Access values, while allowing for contextual variation across systems and disciplines.

Action Area 4: Strengthen public interest infrastructure, standards, and interoperability

Lead Stakeholders: community-led infrastructure providers.

Contributing Stakeholders: Research funding and performing organisations; scholarly communities.

Shared, community governed infrastructure is the backbone of Diamond Open Access and should be developed as a coordinated, interoperable ecosystem rather than a collection of fragmented or duplicative systems.

Public-interest infrastructure should be open, resilient, decentralised, and protected from commercial enclosure, ensuring that scholarly communication remains accessible, inclusive, and governed by the research community.

◇ Integrated, resilient open infrastructure

Strengthen open, community governed scholarly communication infrastructures by investing in interoperable, open-source publishing platforms that integrate repositories and preprint systems as core components. These infrastructures should incorporate persistent identifier ecosystems, long-term preservation, and decentralised, mirrored architectures to ensure resilience, sustainability, and global accessibility, while avoiding fragmentation caused by duplicative proprietary solutions.

◇ Coordinated capacity and technical support

Support and coordinate regional and international Capacity Hubs and Centres as collaborative mechanisms for shared services, knowledge exchange, and technical assistance. These should

provide targeted, context-sensitive support to journals and platforms, enabling them to meet interoperability and quality standards without exclusion.

◇ Open and multilingual metadata as a public good

Invest in and safeguard open, multilingual metadata ecosystems by advancing shared standards, semantic interoperability, and controlled vocabularies, while ensuring that metadata remains a public good protected from enclosure or commercial exploitation.

◇ Interoperable and transparent research workflows

Support the development of interoperable Publish-Review-Curate workflows that enable transparency, version traceability, and the circulation of research across diverse platforms and communities.

◇ Enabling standards and responsible use of AI

Design global standards, interoperability frameworks, and emerging technologies (including AI applications) as enabling, community governed systems that lower barriers to participation. These frameworks should support diverse publishing models and ensure that the use of AI in editorial processes, metadata generation, and discovery is transparent, responsible, and aligned with community values.

◇ Inclusive and non-exclusionary quality assurance

Implement inclusive, layered, and progressive quality assurance frameworks, proportionate to the capacities of journals and platforms; and explicitly avoid “pay-to-play” mechanisms in certification, indexing, or compliance systems that risk marginalising under resourced actors.

Action Area 5: Build capacity and recognise scholarly contributions

Lead Stakeholders: Universities; scholarly communities; research funding organisations.

Contributing Stakeholders: Non-commercial infrastructure providers; libraries; regional training hubs.

Diamond Open Access depends on sustained human capacity and cannot rely on unpaid, invisible, or precarious labour. Editorial, peer review, and governance contributions are foundational to

the scholarly communication system and should be professionalised, formally recognised, and structurally supported within institutional frameworks.

◇ Capacity building through training and skills development

Integrate Diamond Open Access governance, ethical publishing practices, open peer review, and metadata stewardship into doctoral and post-doctoral training programmes, fostering a shared foundation of skills and values across disciplines and regions.

◇ Recognition and institutionalisation of scholarly contributions

Formally recognise and sustainably support editorial labour, peer review, governance participation, and open data stewardship as core scholarly contributions by embedding these roles within institutional structures and reflecting them in workload models, hiring, and promotion criteria, thereby reducing reliance on precarious and invisible labour.

◇ Communities of practice and support infrastructure

Establish and connect structured communities of practice, helpdesks, and regional training hubs to provide coordinated, context-sensitive support for Diamond Open Access journals and platforms.

◇ Sustainable funding and workforce stability

Provide sustained, multi-year support for editorial and technical teams through institutional and funding frameworks, ensuring the long-term stability and resilience of Diamond Open Access infrastructures.

◇ Empowering early career researchers and ensuring continuity

Strengthen the role of Early Career Researchers in Diamond Open Access by ensuring their meaningful representation in editorial and governance bodies, supporting ECR-led initiatives through targeted funding and fellowships, developing structured mentorship frameworks, and fostering international networks and cross-regional collaboration to ensure continuity and global knowledge exchange.

Action Area 6: Advance multilingualism, bibliodiversity, and inclusion

Lead Stakeholders: All stakeholder groups⁴.

Diamond Open Access should strengthen linguistic diversity, inclusive participation, and the representation of diverse knowledge systems within global scholarly communication. A system dominated by a narrow set of languages, regions, or publishing models limits the visibility and accessi-

bility of knowledge and undermines the resilience and relevance of the global knowledge commons. Bibliodiversity is therefore a structural strength that should be actively supported through policy, infrastructure, and evaluation frameworks.

◇ Advance multilingualism and global discoverability

Support scholarly communication in multiple languages alongside English by investing in multilingual publishing practices. This includes funding for journals and books in regional and national languages, as well as the development of multilingual metadata and the translation of titles, abstracts, and keywords. Encourage the responsible use of AI-assisted language technologies, under human oversight, to expand access, while maintaining quality and proper attribution.

◇ Reform research assessment to value diversity and local relevance

Embed multilingualism, bibliodiversity, and inclusion within research evaluation and policy frameworks. Recognise and reward locally-grounded, multilingual scholarship and develop complementary indicators that capture societal relevance, community value, and local impact, beyond conventional metrics.

◇ Strengthen community-led and inclusive scholarly infrastructures

Provide sustained, targeted support for all sizes of community-led Diamond Open Access journals, platforms and repositories, particularly in under-resourced regions and disciplines. Ensure that

⁴. See fn 2 for the 9 stakeholder groups identified in this document.

standards, compliance mechanisms, and interoperability frameworks are proportionate and do not create undue barriers for emerging or smaller initiatives.

◇ Recognise diverse knowledge systems and ensure equitable participation

Acknowledge ancestral, Indigenous, and traditional knowledge-holders as legitimate contributors and co-producers of knowledge. Develop inclusive governance, ethical standards, and attribution practices that respect diverse knowledge systems, while strengthening the visibility, legitimacy, and long-term preservation of local and multilingual scholarly outputs.

Conclusion and Call to Action

The Bengaluru Roadmap and Action Plan affirm that Diamond Open Access is a necessary structural transformation of scholarly communication, which is already practised globally across journals, repositories, platforms, and research communities. Successful implementation requires the alignment of policy, funding and evaluation systems, and the necessary governance to enable Diamond Open Access to function as the primary model for disseminating publicly-funded knowledge. We invite governments, research funding organisations, institutions, and scholarly communities to engage with this Roadmap, to translate

its orientations into concrete action within their respective contexts, and to collaborate across regions toward a coherent and resilient global knowledge commons. The transition to Diamond Open Access is both a shared responsibility and a collective opportunity. Its success will depend on sustained commitment and coordinated action. The Global Summit on Diamond Open Access continues to be the principal gathering of the community. The 4th Global Summit in Bali, Indonesia shall further examine and refine the implementation of the Bengaluru Roadmap and Action Plan.

Organising Institutions

- AmeliCA/Redalyc
- cOAlition S
- Commonwealth Educational Media Centre for Asia (CEMCA)
- CSIR–National Institute of Science Communication and Policy Research (CSIR-NIScPR)
- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
- DST–Centre for Policy Research, IISc (DST-CPR)
- French National Research Agency (ANR)
- Gates Foundation
- German Centre for Research and Innovation, DWIH New Delhi
- ICAR–Directorate of Knowledge Management in Agriculture (ICAR-DKMA), India
- ICAR–Indian Institute of Horticultural Research (ICAR-IIHR)
- IndiaBioscience
- Indian National Young Academy of Science (INYNAS)
- Indo-French Centre for the Promotion of Advanced Research (IFCPAR)
- Information and Library Network (INFLIBNET) Centre, India
- International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT)
- JPN National Centre of Excellence in the Humanities, IIT Indore, India
- Latin American Council of Social Sciences (CLACSO)
- O.P. Jindal Global University (JGU)
- Open Access India
- OPERAS–European Diamond Capacity Hub
- Oscar Ribas University (UOR), Luanda, Angola
- Science Europe
- Society for Promotion of Horticulture (SPH), Bengaluru, India
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Discover more about the 3rd Global Summit on Diamond Open Access:

<https://www.diamondoasummit.org/>

